

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STRESS IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11408393>

Abstract: In this article, the origin of stress and its consequences, as well as the research of gender and age in the use of strategies to overcome stress in students, have been analyzed by local and foreign scientists.

Key words: Stress, psychological protection, depression, psychological stress, emotional state, physiological stress, coping strategies.

Introduction:

Global experts emphasize that stress has become the "*disease of the century*". According to the World Health Organization, 65% of all diseases are caused by stress. According to the records of this organization, at the WHO assembly held in Geneva, stress was included in the International Classification of Diseases under number 11.

A person faces difficult life situations throughout his life. Currently, taking into account the growth of crisis events in the economic and social spheres, the number of complex, crisis situations is increasing significantly. The reason for this may be a lack of experience in overcoming certain life difficulties or insufficient development of personal and environmental resources. As stated in many studies, it is students who fall into relatively high stress situations in such situations.

Due to the state of stress in the world, it causes tension in the human psyche, causing damage to health and life activities. In this regard, the formation of the attitude to fight against the stress that occurs during the education of students who want to have a future profession becomes one of the urgent problems of the day, and it makes the issue of scientific research of the dynamic change of psychological stress in them urgent.

In world educational institutions and scientific centers, scientific researches are being carried out aimed at the dynamics of changes in the state of psychological stress in students and overcoming stress, fighting against stress, using coping strategies such as managing stress, adapting to stress, and maintaining mental stability in stressful situations. Based on the interpretations that the onset of stress is related to the state of anxiety, it is important to moderate the level of tendency to anxiety in order to reduce the effects of stress factors, based on the physiological signs of stress during the educational process, the physiological assessment of the stress of students' educational activities created the need to pay special attention to psychological research aimed at normalization through secrets. Therefore, the research of this problem is of great scientific and practical importance.

D. Abdumadjidova, R. Abdurasulov, D. Boymirzayeva, U. Butayeva, N. Ismoilova, F. Gaziyeva, K. Kadirov, S. Mirzayeva, O. Hayitov, among the psychologists of our republic, provided stability to stress, stressogenic significance of frustration, scientifically researched the psychological aspects of protecting young people from the influence of destructive ideas,

forming the competence of stress management, and activating psychological protection in case situations (unexpected, accidental) in order to prevent the occurrence of stress.

There are different types of stress, which include:

Physiological stress is associated with strong physical and mental effects on the body, while psychological stress is associated with the processes taking place in the psyche of a person, and a person perceives his difficult, extreme situation in his own way. is a mental state consisting of reflection (A.G. Maklakov, S.A. Salekhov). The state of stress appeared under the influence of stressors such as active activity, assessment, inconsistency of activity, physical and natural (S.A. Razumov). Short and long-term stressors are distinguished according to their duration (V. Harris). There are somatic, emotional, behavioral, cognitive signs of stress (L.V. Kakshina, T.L. Shabanova). Anxiety played a major role in the development of stress. Anxiety is an emotional experience characterized by discomfort arising from the uncertainty of the future situation (R.A. Grekhov, Z. Freud, G.S. Sullivan, K. Horney). Personal and reactive anxiety, high social desire, low self-esteem, avoidance of failure, low development of communication skills had a negative impact on students' stress stability (O.V. Lozgacheva). At the same time, the occurrence of anxiety, physiological changes and stress in students during the study process and before the exam was studied (A.N. Akopyan, Y.V. Sapyorova, O.V. Lavrov, T.N. Lisakova). It was found that there is a significant correlation between self-esteem and determinants of tolerant attitude to frustrating situations and stability to stress in students (N.Z. Ismoilova). The prevalence of tension, stressogenicity, and frustration among students shows the urgency of the issue of psychological protection (D.D. Boymirzayeva).

The level of preparation of students for professional activity often depends on the characteristics of their emotional sphere, the ability to achieve success and show good results during the examination period. As a stress factor, the exam takes one of the first places among the various reasons that cause mental stress in students. The consequences of exam stress extend beyond the exam itself and can negatively affect the student's experience post-exam. It should be noted that academic success is determined not only by the level of knowledge, but also by the level of mental stress during training. As exam period is very stressful for most students, coping with stress becomes an important issue. An increase in the level of stress during the examination has a strong impact on mental and somatic health, indicators of cognitive, emotional and physiological processes. Despite the importance of studying the problem, it should be noted that there are no generalizing works on this topic. Recently, the study of "Coping-strategies" as an important conscious mechanism for regulating the behavior and activities of a person is becoming more and more relevant. Definition of methods of coping with stress by Western researchers is reflected in the concept of "Coping" in the sense of "Successful overcoming". R. Lazarus and S. Folkman have developed a set of methods to be implemented by a person to reduce the effects of stress. According to B. D. Karavasarsky, the term "Coping" was used for the first time by L. Murphy in 1962 in the study of problems arising during the development crisis in children. They were concerned with the activity of a person in overcoming complex problems or situations. According to L. Murphy, coping is a person's systemic defense mechanism. However, according to A. V. Libina, coping was used for the first time in 1939 in H. Hartman's work "Ego-psychology and adaptation problems" in the analysis of "conflict and free zones of ME". In 1966, R. Lazarus in his work "Psychological Stress and Coping Process" explained coping as a strategy for overcoming perceived stress and other anxious situations. The term "Coping strategy" is used to define forms of behavior

that overcome difficult life situations. On the basis of coping strategies, various forms of psychological activity covering the internal and external nature of a person's relationship with the object, difficulties, control and avoidance are understood.

After being in a stressful situation, a person starts using mechanisms to overcome stress and turns to coping. If the mechanisms do not produce the expected result, attempts to overcome are continued. If it is not possible to objectively influence the stressor, the subject uses an avoidance strategy. If this is not possible, a cognitive reassessment of the process, which gives it another meaning, is started. Primary and secondary evaluations affect the form, intensity and quality of the reaction to stress. The first step in the cognitive evaluation process is both increasing and decreasing salience to the subject. Based on this assessment, the level of stress load is determined. In connection with this situation, the same situations can have different effects on the stress load. After the individual makes a cognitive assessment of the situation, he begins to identify the mechanisms of overcoming stress - coping. In the case of unsuccessful coping, the stressor remains and the need to continue the coping process arises. In connection with it, the following structure of overcoming is distinguished:

- *acceptance of stress;*
- *cognitive assessment;*
- *developing a coping strategy;*
- *evaluation of the result of actions.*

The problem of studying resources that allow a person to consciously and purposefully overcome, act, predict life events and the results of his actions is relevant for modern psychology. In Russian psychology, V.D. Famous scientists such as Nebilitsin, L.A. Kitayev-Smik, V.A. Bodrov, T.L. Kryukova, N.A. Sirota, L.I. Demans paid attention to this problem. Among them, V.D. Nebilitsyn suggested the classification of individual characteristics of the subject that mediate the influence of stress factors and act as personal resources. It includes the subjective importance of the impact, the characteristics of the previous experience of the individual's activity in similar conditions, the level of development of specific and non-specific adaptation - health, endurance, the level of readiness for activity in these conditions, the attitude of the individual to the activity, the desire to achieve the goal learned. Describing the resource approach to stress regulation, V.A. Bodrov noted that the formation of a resource system and their use in the process of overcoming them is the main factor in resisting stress. By resources, the author understands the functional capabilities that ensure the high level of personal activity, the performance of work tasks, and the achievement of specified indicators within a certain period of time. Based on the concept of resources, a person is able to use all the possibilities of both himself and the environment for the correct distribution of his resources. As stated by V.A. Bodrov, the efficiency of using these resources depends on the parameters describing the task (the value of the load) or the situation (threat level, responsibility, etc.) and the person's capabilities. Describing resources for overcoming stress, V.A. Bodrov distinguishes the following: personal, social, psychological, professional, physical and material. Personal resources include characteristics and attitudes that affect the regulation of behavior in various stressful situations (self-control, self-esteem, self-control, optimism, sense of connection with the world, motivation, etc.). Social resources are represented by the level of social and spiritual support, life values, control of trust (self-confidence, trust), interpersonal relationships, etc. Psychological resources are determined by cognitive, psychomotor, emotional, volitional and other abilities of a person.

Professional resources include the level of knowledge, skills, abilities, and experience necessary to solve problems in a difficult situation. Physical resources are the level of physical and mental health and functional reserves of the body. Material resources reflect financial, housing and other types of personal support. The author considers the above resources to be the sole personal resource of the individual. Analysis of works on the problem of research of personal struggle resources allows to note their diversity. Thus, sources such as temperament type, achievement motivation, locus of control, responsibility, empathy, self-awareness were identified (L.A. Kitayev-Smik, T.L. Kryukova, N.A. Sirota, L.I. Dementi, V.N. Golovanevskaya and others), self-regulation (E.A. Sergienko), psychological defense style (V.A. Ababkov, M. Perret), social competence, intergenerational relations, social groups related to individuals and relationships in them (T.L. Kryukova, S.A. Khazova, E.A. Petrova), professional experience (V.A. Bodrov). Features of style and level of intelligence (A.A. Aleksapolsky), extraversion, affiliation (A.Yu. Malenova), personal activity, emotional stability (E.R. Isayeva), endurance (S. Kobasa, S. Maddiy), optimism (C. Carver, M. Scheier; M. Seligman), self-efficacy (A. Bandura), stubbornness of spirit (V. Frankl), neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, willingness to meet people halfway, consciousness (P.T. Costa, R. McCrae), neuroticism (K. Nakano). In addition to the above, S. Taylor refers to "Additional" personal resources, which include high self-esteem, communication skills, developed social skills and religiosity.

As a conclusion, we can say that the stress that occurs in students in various life situations is manifested not only in negative but also in positive situations. This can sometimes cause depression, but due to situations related to eustress, a person can directly solve the problem in a positive way, in addition, it helps to gain experience to deal with stress, feeling in problematic situations helps to control emotions.

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